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EFFECT OF WEB-BASED MULTIMEDIA TEACHING STRATEGIES ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN WINDING OF ELECTRICAL MACHINES IN GOVERNMENT SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL COLLEGES OF GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study sought to determine the effect of Web-based Multimedia teaching Strategies on Students' Academic Achievement in Winding of electrical machines in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Gombe State. The study was guided by two objectives, two research questions and the corresponding null hypotheses using quasi experimental research design. The population of the study was 100 NTC II Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students with a total sample size of 100 samples using total population sampling techniques. Instruments for data collection was a structured questionnaire tagged Winding of Electrical Machines Achievement Test questionnaire (WEMATQ). The instrument was validated by three experts. The test-retest reliability was used to determine the reliability on 30 NTC II GSTC yola students, using Kuder Richardson (KR-20) and a reliability coefficient index of 0.85 was recorded. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while ANCOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that EIMW students taught Winding of Electrical Machines Using Web-based Multimedia technology teaching Strategies performed better than those taught using the lecture teaching method. Based on the findings, recommendations was made that teachers need to encourage to use Web-based Multimedia teaching Strategies for teaching Winding of Electrical Machines in Government science and technical colleges of Gombe State.

Keywords: Web-Based Multimedia Teaching Strategies, Students' Academic Achievement, Winding of Electrical Machines

INTRODUCTION

Education is a critical driver of socio-economic development, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where there is an increasing emphasis on equipping the youth with the skills necessary for national development. Education serves as a foundation for innovation, empowerment, and the development of human capital. Matheson, (2014). It is essential for fostering societal progress, reducing poverty, and addressing inequalities. In Nigeria, education plays a pivotal role in shaping individuals who can contribute meaningfully to national growth, particularly through vocational and technical training programs that address critical skill shortages. Education is universally recognized as a cornerstone for sustainable development and social transformation.

In recent years, the focus has shifted toward Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as a means of addressing skills gaps in the workforce. TVET plays a vital role in preparing individuals for the labour market by providing

practical skills and competencies that are directly applicable in various industries (Okeke et al., 2022). In Nigeria, TVET has been recognized as a key strategy for promoting industrialization and economic growth, particularly in sectors that require specialized technical knowledge and skills (Adebayo & Adediran, 2021). Within the broader TVET framework, the electrical and electronics trade is one of the most advanced areas of study. The rapid growth of industries reliant on electrical systems has made electrical engineering and associated trades, such as Winding of electrical machines, indispensable. Winding of electrical machines, a specialized skill in electrical engineering, involves the process of winding coils used in transformers, motors, and generators. As the backbone of many electrical and electronic devices, proficiency in Winding of electrical machines is crucial for technical professionals working in power generation, distribution, and repair (Olugbenga et al., 2023). However, students in technical colleges, particularly in Gombe State, often face significant challenges in mastering the theoretical and practical aspects of this specialized skill. Traditional instructional methods, while still prevalent, rely heavily on rote learning and do not always provide students with the interactive and immersive learning experiences required to grasp complex concepts (Olanrewaju, 2023).

Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) is a trade subject offered at the National Technical Certificate (NTC) level in Government Science and Technical College that is geared toward equipping its beneficiaries with knowledge and skills in electrical installation and maintenance practice at the craftsmen level. According to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2016), the philosophy behind the establishment of the National Technical Certificate (NTC) program in Nigeria is to train Technical College Students with the necessary knowledge and skills that could lead to the production of craft men and other skilled personnel who could fill up vacancies of craft level personnel in Nigeria's industrial and business sector. EIMW course is run by the Government Science and Technical College which has been accredited by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) and examined by the National Business and Technical Education Board (NABTEB) in order to ensure that the aim of technical and vocational education of students to performance better both in psychomotor and cognitive development are achieved

Academic achievement of students is a learning outcome that determines the extent to which a student has realized their educational goal and can be measured by many forms of assessment technique. Mustapha (2016), state that students' academic achievement is closely related and influenced by so many factors that include among others school environment, learner's interest, mental ability, availability of facilities and instructional strategies used by teachers. He also opined that instructional strategy in fact is the most influential of all the factors regarding students' achievement. The basis for achieving the goals of teaching and learning in technical and vocational education is to acquaint students with scientific skills, knowledge and enhances their interest in practical skills for self-reliance. Kumazhege and Abdulhamid (2020) state that Academic achievement can be moderated by some factors such as; teaching method, teacher qualification and personality, students' readiness, learning environment, facilities and equipment for the learning to take place.

Among the various platforms for delivering web-based multimedia instruction, Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) has emerged as a widely used Learning Management System (LMS) in educational institutions around the world, including Nigeria. Moodle allows for the creation of multimedia-rich learning environments where instructors can upload instructional videos, quizzes, assignments, and interactive simulations that foster student engagement. As an open-source platform, it has become particularly popular in schools and colleges due to its flexibility, accessibility, and ease of use (Ahmed & Abubakar, 2022). By offering tools that cater to different learning styles, Moodle can significantly enhance the teaching and learning of technical subjects like Winding of electrical machines. Despite the

potential benefits of using web-based multimedia and Moodle in technical education, there is limited research examining their impact specifically in Nigerian technical colleges, particularly in Gombe State. Previous studies (e.g., Aluko et al., 2022) have shown positive results with multimedia interventions in various educational settings. However, their application in the Nigerian context, especially for trades such as Winding of electrical machines, remains underexplored. This study, therefore, aims to evaluate the effectiveness of web-based multimedia instructional strategies, delivered through the Moodle platform, on students' academic achievement and retention in Winding of electrical machines courses at technical government science and colleges in Gombe State. By investigating whether web-based multimedia can improve students' immediate academic achievement and long-term retention of Winding of electrical machines concepts, this research will provide valuable insights into the potential of multimedia-based learning in enhancing technical education in Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It has been observed that the teaching of Winding of electrical machines in Technical Colleges often poses a significant challenge due to the abstract and complex nature of the subject matter. Traditional teaching methods, which rely heavily on lectures method, may not be effective in engaging students and promoting deep understanding of the subject. As a result, students often experience difficulties in achieving academic success of knowledge in Electrical Machines EIMW particularly in the area of winding. Moreover, this can lead to poor academic performance, low motivation, and a lack of interest in pursuing careers in electrical-related fields. Furthermore, the limited use of technology in teaching Electrical Machines may exacerbate these challenges, as students are not exposed to interactive and engaging learning experiences that can enhance their understanding of the subject matter.

This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring the effects of web-based multimedia instructional strategies on students' academic achievement in Winding of electrical machines at technical government science and colleges of Gombe State. By evaluating how these strategies affect both immediate learning outcomes, the study will provide valuable insights into how technology can be leveraged to improve the quality of teaching technical education in Nigeria.

PURPOSES OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study is to determine:

1. The pretest mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods on students' academic achievement in government science and technical colleges of Gombe State
2. The post-test mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods in government science technical colleges of Gombe State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the pretest mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods on students' academic achievement in government science and technical colleges of Gombe State?
2. What are the post-test mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods in government science technical colleges of Gombe State?

HYPOTHESES

The study tested the following null hypotheses:

- HO1:** There is no significant difference between the pretest mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods on students' academic achievement in government science technical colleges of Gombe State.
- HO2:** There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching method on students' academic achievement in government science technical colleges of Gombe State

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study was based on Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML) by Richard Mayer in 2005, the theory describes learning as the processes which take place in the minds of learners during meaningful learning from multimedia instruction, and the theory offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how students process multimedia content. It posits that learners have separate cognitive channels for processing visual and auditory information. According to this theory, multimedia content (i.e., content that integrates both words and images) can be more effective than text or speech alone because it engages multiple cognitive channels simultaneously. As students process these different forms of input, they create mental representations that are richer and more integrated (Mayer, 2022). Mayer's theory is grounded in the notion that human cognitive architecture consists of two channels: the visual/pictorial channel and the verbal/auditory channel. Both channels have limited capacities. When both verbal and visual information are presented in complementary ways, learners can process the information more efficiently and build a deeper understanding. However, cognitive overload can occur if too much information is presented at once, particularly if redundant information is included (Mayer, 2022). For this reason, CTML stresses the importance of balancing multimedia content to avoid overwhelming learners.

Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works is one of the trades offered in Technical Colleges. It is a Vocational trade that exposes students to skills. According to Owoh and Ogwa (2019) Electrical Installation and Maintenance Practice is a program introduced for students to acquire practical skills in electrical works such as maintenance of electrical systems and circuits, electrical Installation, Inspection, and test procedures. According to the National Board for Technical Education (FRN, 2021), Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade are expected to test, diagnose, service, install, and completely repair any fault on electrical machines and equipment using the manufacturer's manual.

The goal of winding of electrical machines is to provide the trainee with the knowledge and skill to enable him wind or rewind (AC and DC) alternating current and direct current rotating/static machine up to 10KVA and appropriate tools and equipment used in winding jobs (NBTE, 2021). Understand and apply all statutory regulations during electrical winding work, acquire skills for preparation and interpretation of winding drawing. An electrical machine is the apparatus that convert energy in three categories: generators which covert mechanical energy to electrical energy, motors which convert electrical energy to mechanical energy and transformers which changes the voltage level of an alternating current. Electric generator is a device that converts mechanical energy to electrical energy. The magnetic field can be provided by electromagnets or permanent magnets mounted on either the rotor or the stator (Chapman, 2018). Lecture method is the art of telling or giving large volumes or quantities of factual information, principles and theories to a large audience without minding whether the audience understands the information being delivered or not, and that learners are expected to go and develop or put flesh on the principles and theories on their own through personal research.

The method or strategy using web-based multimedia teaching strategy is a method employed by teacher in the classroom which plays a vital role in determining and helping students to retain the knowledge they have learned. This study would be based on Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML), which describes learning as the processes that take place in the minds of learners during meaningful learning from multimedia instruction, introduced by Richard Mayer in 2015, offers a comprehensive framework for understanding how students process multimedia content. It posits that learners have separate cognitive channels for processing visual and auditory information. According to this theory, multimedia content (i.e., content that integrates both words and images) can be more effective than text or speech alone because it engages multiple cognitive channels simultaneously. As students process these different forms of input, they create mental representations that are richer and more integrated (Mayer, 2022). Mayer's theory is grounded in the notion that human cognitive architecture consists of two channels: the visual/pictorial channel and the verbal/auditory channel. Both channels have limited capacities. When both verbal and visual information are presented in complementary ways, learners can process the information more efficiently and build a deeper understanding. However, cognitive overload can occur if too much information is presented at once, particularly if redundant information is included (Mayer, 2022). For this reason, CTML stresses the importance of balancing multimedia content to avoid overwhelming learners.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted quasi-experimental research design using pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group for the study. Afuwape & Adeagbo (2018) asserted that quasi experimental design investigates possible cause and effect as well as relationship between two or more variables by the application of treatment which cannot be resolve by description or observation. The area of the study is Gombe State, the state is located in North-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Gombe State is bordered to the west by Bauchi State, to the east by Borno State, to the south-east by Adamawa State, and to the south-west by Taraba State. It is located between longitude 10.36380° N and latitude 11.19280° E. The population of this study comprises of 100 Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work (EIMW) students in NTC II who are taught Winding of Electrical Machines in government science and technical colleges in Gombe State. The population comprises of 75 males' students and 25 female students' offering the course. The sample ad sampling technique for the study was purposive total population sampling used for the study because the population was not much and can be managed for the study also all the sampled area has sufficient facilities and availability of the required resources for practical sessions. Simple random sampling was then used to assign Technical Colleges into experimental and control groups. Two instruments were used for the Data collection, which was tagged "Winding of Electrical Machines Achievement Test" (WEMAT). The Achievement Test were based on 40 objectives questions with their options lettered A-D Adopted by the researcher from NABTEB past question paper year (2019). The instruments (WEMAT) were validated by three experts from Modibbo Adama University Yola. Reliability of the instrument was determined by pilot testing the instruments in Adamawa State which is not part of the study area but have the same characteristics with the study area specifically; Government Science and Technical College, Yola was used for the reliability test. The instrument was trial tested on 20 NTC II students in GSTC in Yola using test-retest method. The data obtained was analyzed using Kuder-Richardson formula 20 (KR-20) formula and reliability coefficient index of 8.20 was obtained. The data for this study was analyzed using mean and standard deviation with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. T-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The cut-off points were in line with NABTEB rating 100-50 marks is accepted as pass mark while below is rejected as fail.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the pretest mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods on students’ academic achievement in government science and technical colleges of Gombe State?

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviations of Pre-Test Mean Scores of Students Taught Winding of Electrical Machines Using Web-Based Multimedia Instructional Strategies and Lecture Method

Teaching Method	N	\bar{x}	SD
Web-based multimedia instructional strategies	53	30.79	7.43
Lecture Method	47	29.79	9.09

N = Number of Respondents, \bar{x} = Mean, SD. = Standard Deviation

Table 1 sought to determine the pretest mean scores of students taught Winding of electrical machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies compared to those taught using the lecture method in government science and technical colleges in Gombe State. The result shows that students exposed to web-based multimedia instructional strategies had a slightly higher pretest mean score of 30.79 with a standard deviation of 7.43, while those taught using the lecture method had a mean score of 29.79 and a standard deviation of 9.09. This indicates that before the instructional intervention, both groups had comparable levels of prior knowledge, with a marginal difference in favour of the web-based group.

Research Question 2

What are the post-test mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods in government science technical colleges of Gombe State?

Table 2: Means and Standard Deviations of Post-Test Mean score of Students Taught Winding of Electrical Machines Using Web-Based Multimedia Instructional Strategies and Lecture Method

Test	Pre-Test			Post-Test			MD
	N	\bar{x}	SD	N	\bar{x}	SD	
Web-based Multimedia Instructional Strategies	53	30.79	7.43	53	74.66	7.07	43.87
Lecture Method	47	29.79	9.09	47	57.60	11.85	27.81
Mean Gain		1.00			17.07		

N= Number of Students, \bar{x} = Mean Scores, SD = Standard Deviation, MD = Mean Difference, Mean Difference = Post-test Scores minus Pretest Scores, Mean Gain = Post-test Scores of Web-based Multimedia Instructional Strategies minus Post-test Scores of Lecture Method

Table 2 presents the pre-test and post-test mean scores and standard deviations of students taught Winding of electrical machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and the lecture method in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Gombe State. Students in the web-based multimedia group (N = 53) had a pre-test mean score of 30.79 (SD = 7.43) and a post-test mean of 74.66 (SD = 7.07), resulting in a mean difference (MD) of 43.87. In comparison, students taught using the lecture method (N = 47) had a pre-test mean of 29.79 (SD = 9.09) and a post-test mean of 57.60 (SD = 11.85), with a mean difference of 27.81. The mean gain between the post-test scores of both groups is 17.07 in favour of the web-based multimedia instructional strategy. This indicates that students taught with web-based multimedia instructional strategies

performed better than those taught with the lecture method, suggesting the effectiveness of multimedia tools in enhancing learning outcomes in Winding of electrical machines.

Hypothesis Testing

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the pretest mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching methods on students’ academic achievement in government science technical colleges of Gombe State.

Table 3: t- test Comparison of Pre-Test Mean Scores of Students Taught Winding of Electrical Machines Using Web-Based Multimedia Instructional Strategies and those taught using Lecture Method

Teaching Method	N	\bar{x}	S ²	df	T	P-Value	Remark
Web-based Multimedia Instructional Strategies	53	30.79	7.42				
				98	0.61	0.54	Accept
Lecture Method	47	29.79	9.08				

N= Number of Students, \bar{x} = Mean Scores, σ = Standard Deviation, df = Degree of Freedom

Table 3 answered hypothesis one which tested whether there was a significant difference in the pretest mean scores of students taught Winding of electrical machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and those taught using the lecture method in government science and technical colleges in Gombe State. Table 3 presents the t-test result, showing that students in the web-based (experimental) group had a mean score of 30.79, while those in the lecture (control) group had a mean of 29.79. The calculated t-value was 0.61 with a p-value of 0.54, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that there was no statistically significant difference in the pretest scores between the two groups.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the post-test mean scores of students taught Winding of Electrical Machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and lecture teaching method on students’ academic achievement in government science technical colleges of Gombe State

Table 4: t- test Comparison of Post-Test Mean Scores of Students Taught Winding of Electrical Machines Using Web-Based Multimedia Instructional Strategies and those taught using Lecture Method

Teaching Method	N	\bar{x}	S ²	df	T	P-Value	Remark
Web-based Multimedia Instructional Strategies	53	74.66	7.07				
				98	8.86	0.00	Reject
Lecture Method	47	57.60	11.85				

N= Number of Students, \bar{x} = Mean Scores, σ = Standard Deviation, df = Degree of Freedom

Table 4 above showed the result of the testing of research hypothesis two. Table 4 shows that the web-based multimedia group had a higher mean score of 74.66, compared to 57.60 for the lecture method group. The calculated t-value

was 8.86 with a p-value of 0.00, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a statistically significant difference in post-test achievement between the two groups. Hence, there was a significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students taught Winding of electrical machines using web-based multimedia instructional strategies and those taught using the lecture method in government science and technical colleges of Gombe State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that before the treatment, students in both the web-based multimedia instructional strategies group and the lecture method group had comparable pre-test mean scores. This indicates that the students had a similar level of prior knowledge in Winding of electrical machines before the treatment was administered. The finding is in agreement with Ogunlade and Ajiboye (2021), who emphasized the importance of establishing equivalence in learners' entry behaviour to ensure the validity of instructional outcomes in comparative studies. Their research highlighted that when students in different instructional groups have comparable pre-test scores, any subsequent differences in achievement can be attributed to the teaching methods rather than pre-existing knowledge gaps. Similarly, Emmanuel et al. (2021) supported this by stating that balanced pre-test achievement across experimental and control groups provides a solid foundation for evaluating the impact of instructional strategies, particularly in digital learning environments. In their study, they found that comparable pre-intervention achievement levels enhance the reliability of attributing learning gains to the instructional approach used. This finding is also consistent with the views of Sulaimon and Durojaiye (2020), who noted that achieving baseline equality in experimental research strengthens the credibility of comparisons and conclusions. In their investigation of technology-driven teaching in technical education, they affirmed that equal starting points are essential for accurately assessing the effectiveness of instructional interventions.

The findings of the study revealed that students taught using web-based multimedia instructional strategies had significantly higher post-test mean scores compared to those taught using the lecture method. This demonstrates that web-based multimedia instruction was more effective in enhancing students' academic achievement in Winding of electrical machines. The finding is in agreement with Adams and Salau (2020), who reported that students exposed to web-based instructional strategies performed significantly better than those taught using traditional methods. Their study on digital instructional approaches in technical education showed that multimedia resources enhance students' understanding and engagement, leading to improved academic achievement. Similarly, the finding supports Olaniyan and Ajayi (2021), who found that integrating multimedia tools into instruction leads to better learning outcomes compared to conventional lecture methods. According to their research, multimedia instruction provides a more interactive and stimulating learning environment that facilitates comprehension and retention. In the same vein, Ibrahim and Yusuf (2022) concluded that students taught with web-based multimedia platforms achieved higher academic results due to the flexible, visual, and self-paced nature of the digital content. Their study highlighted that the use of videos, animations, and interactive simulations makes abstract concepts more concrete, particularly in technical subjects like Winding of electrical machines.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the use of web-based multimedia instructional strategies significantly enhances students' academic achievement in winding of electrical machines compared to the traditional lecture method. While both groups started with similar levels of knowledge as indicated by the pretest scores, students taught using

multimedia strategies outperformed their counterparts in the post-test mean scores. This suggests that web-based multimedia strategy used in teaching technical subjects can lead to more effective learning outcomes by increasing students' engagement, understanding, and long-term retention of content taught. Therefore, use of multimedia instructional strategies is a viable and beneficial approach to improving teaching and learning in government science and technical colleges in Gombe State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers in technical colleges should administer pre-tests when carrying out research in teaching Winding of Electrical Machines. This will help them assess students' entry-level knowledge and design instruction that meets their specific learning needs.
2. Teachers in technical colleges should adopt web-based multimedia instructional strategies in the teaching of Winding of Electrical Machines, as these strategies have been shown to improve students' academic achievement more effectively than lecture-only methods.

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